

Synthesis and characterization of oxothiomolybdenum(VI) complexes of some ONS chelating ligands by *in situ* oxo removal and sulphido insertion in the corresponding dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes

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Abstract : This work reports the synthesis, characterization and electrochemical studies of several $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{OS}]^{2+}$ complexes of some tridentate ONS donor ligands obtained by the condensation of salicylaldehyde/2-hydroxyacetophenone with S-benzyl and S-methyl dithiocarbazates. In this work PPh_3 and PPh_3S mixture is used as the synthetic reagent. The general strategy of synthesizing the complexes of the $[\text{MoOSL}]$ type with the $[\text{MoOS}]^{2+}$ core from corresponding complexes with the $[\text{MoO}_2]^{2+}$ core by *in situ* oxoremoval-sulphide addition process. Presence of the oxothio core in all the $[\text{MoOSL}]$ complexes is established by their reaction with KCN resulting in the formation of the CNS^- species. All the complexes are characterized by various spectroscopic (NMR, IR, UV-Vis) techniques and also by cyclic voltammetry. All the complexes exhibit an irreversible overall 2 electron reductive response probably by proton assisted loss of the sulphido group leading to the formation of the corresponding $[\text{MoOL}]$ complex.

Keywords : Oxothiomolybdenum(VI) complexes, dithiocarbazate, Schiff bases, PPh_3S .

Introduction

The presence of the oxothiomolybdenum(VI) active sites in the oxidized xanthine oxidase and related enzymes has been proposed and established¹⁻¹³. Current studies pointed to the presence of an apical oxo-ligand and equatorial sulphide ligand at the Mo-site of xanthine oxidase¹⁴. Reports of some model systems containing such oxothiomolybdenum(VI) center has also been published^{10,15-17}. Importance of sulphide ligation in the molybdenum catalysis in redox processes involving molybdoenzymes was realized¹⁸ and that led to studies on sulfur-rich complexes of molybdenum. Even then complexes involving the $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{OS}]^{2+}$ center are rather rare and are quite unstable¹⁹. The difficulties experienced in the synthesis of complexes with the $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{OS}]^{2+}$ center are the ease of reduction of Mo^{VI} by the thio-ligand as well as reactivity of the thio-ligand itself²⁰.

This work reports the synthesis, characterisation and electrochemical studies of several $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{OS}]^{2+}$ complexes of some tridentate ONS donor ligands

obtained by the condensation of salicylaldehyde/2-hydroxyacetophenone with S-benzyl and S-methyl dithiocarbazates. In this work PPh_3 and PPh_3S mixture is used as the synthetic reagent. It is possible that the PPh_3 produces the $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}]^{2+}$ species by oxo-abstraction which is followed by oxidative addition of sulfur from the PPh_3S .

Experimental

Materials :

$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2]$ was prepared as described in the literature²¹. Reagent grade solvents were dried and distilled prior to use. All other chemicals used for preparative work were of reagent grade, available commercially and used without further purification.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 240 C, H, N analyzer. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 300 L NMR spectrometer operating at 300 MHz with TMS as internal standard. IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on a Perkin-

Elmer model 883 infrared spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a HITACHI U-3501 UV-Vis recording spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured with a PAR model 155 vibrating sample magnetometer with $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. Electrochemical data were collected on a Sycopel model AEW2 1820 F/S instrument at 298 K using a Pt working electrode, Pt auxiliary electrode and SCE reference electrode. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in DMF containing 0.1 M TEAP as supporting electrolyte.

Synthesis of the ligands :

S-Benzyl-β-N-(2-hydroxyphenyl)methylene dithiocarbamate (H_2L^1) :

A mixture of 10 ml (0.2 mol) hydrazine hydrate and 11.2 g (0.2 mol) KOH in 70 ml of 90% ethanol was cooled down to -10°C . 15 ml (0.25 mol) of carbon disulphide was added dropwise with constant stirring. The yellow oil which had formed was separated and dissolved in previously cooled 60 ml of 40% ethanol. To it 23 ml (0.2 mol) of benzyl chloride was added slowly with vigorous stirring. The white product which had formed was collected and after recrystallization from benzene was dissolved in 50 ml of absolute ethanol. To this solution a 21.5 ml (0.2 mol) of salicylaldehyde in 50 ml ethanol was added. The resultant mixture was heated on a steam bath for about 10 min. The crystals which had settled down were filtered off, washed with ethanol and recrystallized from benzene and dried *in vacuo*. Yield ~80%, m.p. ~185 °C (Found : C, 59.71; H, 4.80; N, 9.43. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$: C, 59.60; H, 4.64; N, 9.30%).

IR (KBr pellet), cm^{-1} : $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ 3100 (m), $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ 3425 (sh), $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ 1617 (s), 1604 (s), $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ 1311 (s); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) : (-CH=N-) 8.04 s (1), (-CH₂-) 4.59 s (2), (-NH-) 10.02 s, (aromatic -OH) 10.72 b (1), (aromatic proton) 6.92–6.98 m (2), 7.24–7.43 m (7).

S-Methyl-β-N-(2-hydroxyphenyl)methylene dithiocarbamate (H_2L^2) :

This was prepared by following the same procedure only by taking 12.5 mL (0.2 mol) of methyl iodide instead of benzyl chloride. Yield ~80%, m.p. ~210 °C (Found : C, 48.12; H, 4.39; N, 12.53. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$: C, 47.79; H, 4.42; N, 12.39%).

IR (KBr pellet), cm^{-1} : $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ 3112 (m), $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ 3430 (sh), $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ 1619 (s), 1604 (m), $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ 1315 (s); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) : (-CH=N-) 8.01 s (1), (-NH-) 10.09 s (1), (-CH₃) 2.56 s (3), (aromatic -OH) 10.24 b (1), (aromatic proton) 6.93–7.06 m (2), 7.25–7.40 m (2).

The Schiff base ligands *S*-benzyl-β-*N*-(2-hydroxyphenylethylidene)dithiocarbamate (H_2L^3) and *S*-methyl-β-*N*-(2-hydroxyphenylethylidene)dithiocarbamate (H_2L^4) were prepared by condensing *S*-benzyl and *S*-methyl dithiocarbamates²² with 2-hydroxyacetophenone in ethanol. The ligands have been satisfactorily characterized by elemental analysis, IR and $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectral data.

S-Benzyl-β-N-(2-hydroxyphenylethylidene)dithiocarbamate (H_2L^3) :

Yield ~80%, m.p. ~148 °C (Found : C, 60.26; H, 4.65; N, 8.73. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$: C, 60.76; H, 5.06; N, 8.86%).

IR (KBr pellet), cm^{-1} : $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ 3171 (m), $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ 3436 (sh), $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ 1600 (s), $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ 1309 (m); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) : ($\text{H}_3\text{C-C=N-}$) 2.47 s (3), (-CH₂-) 4.51 s (2), (-NH-) 11.25 s (1), (aromatic -OH) 11.26 s (1), (aromatic proton) 6.84–6.90 m (2), 7.24–7.41 m (7).

S-Methyl-β-N-(2-hydroxyphenylethylidene)dithiocarbamate (H_2L^4) :

Yield ~75%, m.p. ~160 °C (Found : C, 49.80; H, 4.98; N, 11.71. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$: C, 50.00; H, 5.00; N, 11.66%).

IR (KBr pellet), cm^{-1} : $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ 3173 (m), $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ 3432 (sh), $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ 1600 (s), $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ 1344 (m); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) : ($\text{H}_3\text{C-C=N-}$) 2.46 s (3), (-NH-) 11.42 s (1), (-CH₃) 2.55 s (3), (aromatic -OH) 12.68 s (1), (aromatic proton) 6.86–6.99 m (2), 7.3 t (1), 7.6 d (1).

Synthesis of complexes :

MoOSL¹ (1) : To a refluxing solution of 0.428 g (1.0 mmol) of MoO_2L^1 in 20 ml dry degassed dichloromethane, 2.94 g (10.0 mmol) of PPh_3S and 0.393 g (1.5 mmol) of PPh_3 in 15 ml dry degassed dichloromethane were added simultaneously. The resulting reddish brown solution was refluxed for 1 h when a reddish brown solid separated out. The product was filtered and washed several times with degassed hot dichloromethane and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of MoOSL⁴ (4) in DMF solution

CaCl₂. Yield ~70% (Found : C, 41.43; H, 3.11; N, 5.94; Mo, 20.98. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂N₂S₃O₂Mo : C, 40.54 ; H, 2.70; N, 6.31; Mo, 21.62%).

IR (KBr pellet), cm⁻¹ : ν_{C=N} 1591 (vs), ν_{Mo=O} 969 (vs), ν_{Mo-S} 392 (m), ν_{Mo=S} 530 (m), ν_{Mo-N} 630 (s); UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂) [λ_{max}/nm (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 310 (6645), 410 (5354), 465 (5432); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : (-CH=N-) 9.04 s (1), (-CH₂-) 4.45 s (2), (aromatic proton) 6.88–7.13 m (2), 7.25–7.83 m (7).

Compounds **2**, **3** and **4** were prepared by following the method described above for the preparation of MoOSL¹ (**1**). Yield ~70–75%.

MoOSL² (**2**) : (Found : C, 29.64; H, 2.32 ; N, 7.40; Mo, 25.96. Calcd. for C₉H₈N₂S₃O₂Mo : C, 29.35; H, 2.17; N, 7.61; Mo, 26.08%); IR (KBr pellet), cm⁻¹ : ν_{C=N} 1584 (vs), ν_{Mo=O} 961 (vs), ν_{Mo-S} 385 (m), ν_{Mo=S} 525 (m), ν_{Mo-N} 625 (s); UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂) [λ_{max}/nm (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 309 (5577), 410 (4622), 464 (5043); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : (-CH=N-) 8.96 s (1), (-CH₂-) 2.60 s (3), (aromatic proton) 6.95–7.11 m (2), 7.55–7.80 m (2).

MoOSL³ (**3**) : (Found : C, 41.53; H, 2.90; N, 5.85; Mo, 21.00. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₂S₃O₂Mo : C, 41.92; H, 3.06; N, 6.11; Mo, 20.96%); IR (KBr pellet), cm⁻¹ : ν_{C=N} 1595 (vs), ν_{Mo=O} 971 (vs), ν_{Mo-S} 390 (m), ν_{Mo=S} 519 (m), ν_{Mo-N} 632 (s); UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂) [λ_{max}/nm (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 303 (3335), 387 (2439), 472 (2577); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : (H₃C-C=N-) 2.80 s (3), (-CH₂-) 4.47 s (2), (aromatic proton) 6.91–7.11 m (2), 7.28–7.53 m (7).

MoOSL⁴ (**4**) : (Found : C, 32.10; H, 2.47; N, 7.10; Mo, 24.71. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₀N₂S₃O₂Mo : C, 31.41; H, 2.62; N, 7.33; Mo, 25.13%); IR (KBr pellet), cm⁻¹ : ν_{C=N} 1595 (vs), ν_{Mo=O} 966 (vs), ν_{Mo-S} 380 (m), ν_{Mo=S} 520 (m), ν_{Mo-N} 630 (s); UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂) [λ_{max}/nm (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 298 (5596), 388 (4248), 470 (4810); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : (H₃C-C=N-) 2.81 s (3), (-CH₂-) 2.59 s (3), (aromatic proton) 6.91–6.94 dd (1), 7.06–7.11 m (1), 7.48–7.53 m (1), 7.90–7.92 dd (1).

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of the ligands :

The Schiff base ligands (H₂L¹, H₂L², H₂L³ and H₂L⁴) were prepared using a published procedure²² by condensing S-benzyl and S-methyl dithiocarbazates with salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenone in ethanol. Elemental analysis, IR and ¹H NMR data corresponded exactly to those reported earlier.

Synthesis and characterization of oxothiomolybdenum(vi) complexes :

The oxothiomolybdenum(vi) complexes MoOSL¹ (**1**), MoOSL² (**2**), MoOSL³ (**3**) and MoOSL⁴ (**4**) were prepared by refluxing the corresponding dioxomolybdenum(vi) [MoO₂L] compounds with PPh₃S and PPh₃ in dry, degassed CH₂Cl₂ under dry N₂ atmosphere in the mole ratio 1 : 10 : 1.5.

Synthesis of [Mo^{VI}OSL] complex is known to be difficult due to the reduction of Mo^{VI} center by S²⁻²⁰. The general strategy of synthesizing the Mo^{VI} complexes with [Mo^{VI}OS]²⁺ core from the Mo^{VI} complexes with [Mo^{VI}O₂]²⁺ core *in situ* 'oxo removal-sulfido addition' process, where a large excess of PPh₃S put into the reaction sphere. Again, the elemental analyses suggest that unlike [Mo^{VI}O₂L] complexes, these [Mo^{VI}OSL] complexes do not have any solvent molecule attached to the vacant sixth coordination point of the acceptor center. Larger volume of sulfur atom and a Mo=S bond inclined below the ONS meridian of the Schiff base ligand partially obstructs the sixth coordination site. The Mo site should therefore be preferably pentacoordinated and reluctant to be engaged in polymerization.

We could not isolate single crystals of any of these compounds, presumably due to their instability in solution on keeping for a long time. It has been observed that, [Mo^{VI}OSL] react with KCN and the sulfur atom of the Mo=S bond is converted to SCN⁻ in solution, which is detected in the filtrate by the characteristic blood-red colouration produced on addition of Fe³⁺.

This reaction is mimetic of the deactivation of xanthine oxidase upon cyanolysis^{20,23–26}. Composition of the [Mo^{VI}OSL] complexes have been arrived at on the basis of elemental analyses. Molybdenum was estimated gravimetrically by using oxine as the reagent by standard method²⁷. All the complexes are fairly soluble in alcohol, CH₂Cl₂, CH₃CN, DMF and DMSO and are air stable at room temperature in the solid state. They are found to be diamagnetic as all of them contain the d⁰Mo^{VI} center²⁸. Molar conductivity data in 10⁻³ M CH₂Cl₂ solution indicate that they are non-electrolytes. Electrochemical characteristics of the complexes were examined by cyclic voltammetry at a platinum disc electrode in DMF solution with TEAP as supporting electrolyte.

During the present study it is observed that the MoOSL complexes in DCM/DMF solution undergo spontaneous transformation to the corresponding MoO₂L complexes reported before²². Spectrum of the complex is recorded in solution at an interval of 15 min. It was found that character of this spectrum, its optical density at λ_{max} and ε value remained constant up to one hour. After one hour, the optical density at λ_{max} began to change slowly along with the shift of λ_{max} and ultimately became identical with the precursor complex MoO₂L. Therefore, all solution studies are performed well within one hour after MoOSL dissolved in DCM/DMF, so that the complex species present in solution is exclusively MoOSL.

IR and ¹H NMR spectra :

Some characteristic IR bands of oxothiomolybdenum(vi) complexes are presented in Experimental section. A strong ν_{C=N} band^{29,30} was observed around 1585–1595 cm⁻¹ region for the complexes indicating the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen^{29–31} to the oxothiomolybdenum(vi) center.

Only a single strong band at ~965 cm⁻¹ appear due to ν_{Mo=O} as opposed to the twin symmetric and antisymmetric stretching bands for the [MoO₂]²⁺ moiety in [Mo^{VI}O₂L]. However, the simultaneous presence of Mo=S at the same metal center may also have some role to play in governing the Mo=O bond stretching frequency leading to an optimum use of metal d-orbitals^{32–35}. A new band around ~630 cm⁻¹ region was observed for complexes and is assigned to the ν_{Mo–N} mode³². The medium intensity band around ~385 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_{Mo–S}^{36,37}. The band at ~520 cm⁻¹ region is assigned to the ν_{Mo=S}, which is corroborated by comparison to (NH₄)₂[MoS₄] and is also supported by previous works^{6–8,20,38–40}.

¹H NMR data for the ligands and their corresponding complexes in DMSO-*d*₆ are given in Experimental section. The relatively broad signals at δ 10.72 and 10.02; δ 10.24 and 10.09; δ 11.25 and 11.26; δ 11.42 and 12.68 in the ¹H NMR spectra corresponding to O–H and N–H of the ligand H₂L¹, H₂L², H₂L³ and H₂L⁴ are found to disappear in the complexes **1**, **2**, **3** and **4** respectively as a result of complexation. The signals at δ 8.04 and 8.01 of the ligands have shifted downfield to δ 9.04 and 8.96, indicating coordination from the azomethine nitrogen in the complexes **1** and **2**. In the complexes **3** and **4**, the involvement of the azomethine nitrogen is indicated by the shift of the –CH₃ proton signal from δ 2.47 to 2.80 and δ 2.46 to 2.81 respectively. The methylene protons of the ligands and their corresponding complexes **1** and **3** appearing at δ 4.59 and 4.45, δ 4.51 and 4.47 indicate that the S-benzyl sulfur is not involved in the coordination. The nine aromatic protons appear as multiplets within the range δ 7.24–7.43 (7 protons), δ 6.92–6.98 (2 protons), δ 7.24–7.41 (7 protons) and δ 6.64–6.90 (2 protons) for the ligands H₂L¹ and H₂L³ respectively. Similar observation for aromatic protons has been made with the ligand H₂L² and H₂L⁴ and their corresponding complexes. The methyl protons of the ligand H₂L² and H₂L⁴ and their complexes appear at nearly the same position.

Analysis of IR and NMR spectra of the reported MoOSL complexes clearly indicates that coordination to the Mo-center occurs through phenolate oxygen, azomethine nitrogen and thioenolate sulfur, one of the

two oxo-oxygen of MoO_2L being substituted by sulfur. Thus, structure of such a MoOSL complex is expected to be similar to that of its precursor MoO_2L which is previously reported by us²².

Electronic spectra :

Electronic spectra of the oxothiomolybdenum(vI) complexes were recorded in dry dichloromethane and the spectral data of complexes are presented in Experimental section. The lowest energy absorption maxima is located in the 470–385 nm range and may be assigned^{38,41} to the thiolato $\text{S}(\text{p}\pi)\text{-Mo}(\text{d}\pi)$ LMCT transition due to the promotion of an electron from the filled HOMO of the ligand of primarily sulfur $\text{p}\pi$ character to the empty LUMO of molybdenum $\text{d}\pi$ character. Other LMCT bands are observed in the region 385–300 nm^{31,42–44} and may be assigned to the nitrogen to molybdenum and the oxygen to molybdenum charge transfer processes respectively⁴¹. The bands appearing below 300 nm are probably due to intra-ligand transitions.

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric results^a (V vs SCE) for oxothiomolybdenum(vI) complexes at 298 K

Complexes	E_{pc} (V)
MoOSL ¹ (1)	-0.89
MoOSL ² (2)	-0.90
MoOSL ³ (3)	-0.87
MoOSL ⁴ (4)	-0.88

^aSolvent : DMF (dry, degassed); supporting electrolyte : 0.1 M TEAP; solution strength : 10^{-3} M; working electrode : platinum; reference electrode : SCE; scan rate : 100 mV s⁻¹.

Electrochemical properties :

The electron transfer behaviour of the oxothiomolybdenum(vI) complexes (1-4) has been examined in dry degassed DMF solution using cyclic voltammetry at a platinum electrode with 0.1 M TEAP as the supporting electrolyte over a potential range of 0.0 to -1.4 V. The numerical data are presented in Table 1 and a representative voltammogram is shown in Fig. 1. All the complexes are found to exhibit one step two-electron reduction in the potential window scanned as was evidenced from a comparison with authentic 2 electron systems^{22,45}. As is expected the MoOSL complexes are found to undergo more facile reduction at⁴⁶ the molybdenum center than the corresponding

MoO_2L complexes. Since all the complexes undergo an overall 2 electron reduction, proton assisted loss of the sulphido group to form $[\text{MoO}]^{2+}$ complex is more likely. The source of proton may be the trace of water in DMF.

Concluding remarks :

Oxothiomolybdenum(vI) complexes of the MoOSL type using four ONS chelating ligands have been prepared by a method of oxoabstraction followed by thioinclusion method effected by a combination $\text{PPh}_3\text{-PPh}_3\text{S}$. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, spectroscopic techniques (UV-Vis, IR, NMR), magnetic susceptibility measurement and by cyclic voltammetry. Like the few other MoOSL-type of complexes reported till date these compounds are susceptible to solvolysis and are found to get converted slowly into the corresponding dioxomolybdenum species. However, they are stable in solution for a sufficient time to allow complete characterization of the complexes (UV-Vis, IR, NMR, conductivity and CV) in solution. Because of their instability in solution, molybdenum(vI) complexes containing the $[\text{MoOS}]^{2+}$ core are rather scarce. They bear resemblance to the active site of the oxidized form of xanthine oxidase. As MoOSL complex is obtained from their structurally characterized MoO_2L precursor by the replacement of one of the oxo-group by a thio group, a MoOSL complex is expected to be structurally similar to its MoO_2L analogue. This expectation receives further support from the fact that a MoOSL complex is reconverted into the corresponding MoO_2L complex on solvolysis.

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